

Effective mitigation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from drained peatlands requires an understanding of the combined effects of soil characteristics, soil water dynamics and farming practices. Varying peat depth in a drained peatland influences its water table levels, with a consequent impact on GHG exchange. The aim of this study is to compare simulation results of CO₂ emissions with the observations and to assess the effect of the changes in water table levels on these emission rates across a gradient of peat depth. The simulations are performed for the Luke Ruukki experimental station and are run with the process-based ecosystem model LandscapeDNDC, which incorporates soil properties and management practices, as well as weather drivers, to simulate the carbon and nitrogen cycles of the landscape at a time resolution of one hour. The experimental site is divided into eight study plots with peat depths varying from 20 to 80 cm and there is a controlled subsurface drainage system in the field. Each study plot has four groundwater pipes and two of them equipped with sensors measuring continuously water table level. In addition, each plot has a Soil Scout system measuring soil moisture from three depths. The plots were cultivated with forage grasses for the years 2019-2021 during which also the measurements of respiration rates and soil properties were collected.

The simulations are first evaluated against a set of measurements of CO₂ exchange based on both chamber and eddy covariance (EC) techniques collected during the three growing seasons. We measured the ecosystem respiration from eight study plots with varying peat depth using chamber technique. This allows us to correlate CO₂ fluxes with peat depth. The EC system, on the other hand, provided a continuous measurement of the net ecosystem exchange at the site scale. Such a measurement setup allows us to simultaneously evaluate how the model captures the temporal and spatial variability of the CO₂ fluxes from the agricultural peatland. Measurements of soil moisture and temperature at the chamber locations are used to assess the model's ability to simulate the soil heat and water exchange patterns within the soil.

After analysing the simulations with the field observations, we evaluate the CO₂ emissions under simplified management scenarios by changing the water table level in the model input, and observe the changes in respiration in the model output. By varying the peat layer properties in the model we are able to simulate how peat layers of different thickness respond to changes in water table depth. As a result, the study provides insights into how the attributes of the peat soils are affecting the respiration rates and how the hydrological changes can be used to alter these ecological processes.